

FUNDAMENTALS OF SINGING IN THE PERFORMANCE OF UZBEK MUSICAL ART.

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Annotation: This article provides detailed information about the ancient formation processes and essence of Uzbek music performance, the traditions of singing teacher-student in music performance, and the departments of performance skills.

Keywords: music, culture, tradition, status, scientist, musicologist, vocal, ancient times, people, musical instrument performance.

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada o'zbek musiqa san'ati ijrochiligining qadimiy shakllanish jarayonlari va mazmun-mohiyati, musiqa san'ati ijrochiligida xonandalik ustoz-shogird an'analari, ijrochilik mahoratini bo'limlari haqida batafsil ma'lumot berilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: musiqa, madaniyat, an'ana, maqom, olim, musiqashunos, vokal, qadimgi davr, xalq, cholg'u ijrochiligi.

Аннотация: В данной статье представлена подробная информация о древних процессах формирования и сущности узбекского музыкального исполнительства, традициях пения наставника-ученика в музыкальном исполнительстве, отделах исполнительского мастерства.

Ключевые слова: музыка, культура, традиция, статус, ученый, музыковед, вокал, древность, народ, музыкально-инструментальное исполнительство.

Over the past period, the Republic of Uzbekistan has adopted a number of normative and legal acts on the development of culture and arts[1]. In particular, the Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PD - 3391 of November 17, 2017 " On measures to further develop the art of the Uzbek national makom", of May 30, 2019 " On the organization of the activities of the state museum-reserves Sarmishsay", "Shakhrisabz", "Termez" and "Kokand" Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. 443 of April 21 [2] , 2020 "On measures to further increase the efficiency of the fine and applied arts" Resolution No. PD - 4688 of May 26, 2020 "Culture Decree No. PD-6000 of May 23 [3].Ensuring the development and prospects of the Republic of Uzbekistan depends on the changes taking place in the economic, social, political and cultural spheres, and in order to actively participate in such changes, high-level general and special knowledge, intellectual capacity, broad outlook and

skillful use of information communications are required. Based on these requirements, the training of pedagogic personnel is one of the most important tasks of today.

In the performance of Uzbek music art, singing passed from teacher to student on the basis of tradition, developed and reached us despite various conditions, sometimes developing and sometimes encountering certain contradictions. Folklore sayings in folk music belonging to the layer of Uzbek musical heritage or professional music in the oral tradition - statuses, the vocal and modern music performance, which has been developing from the beginning of the 19th century, has its main position in the folk art. It is worth noting. Each of the above-mentioned directions has its own style, rules, and forms in terms of its form and performance. Among them I. Rajabov, F. Karomatov, T. Gafurbekov, O. Ibrokhimov, R. Yunusov, N. Toshtemirov, O. Bekov, S. Bekmatov, O. Toshmatova, D. Mullajonov, K. Panjiev. It is permissible to mention the names of Gods. In their scientific research, they provided valuable information about the performance style, musical form and folk style of singing, which was formed on the basis of historical experiences and embodied the most perfect traditions, and the types and characteristics of melodies decorated with national colors. Singing performance not only shows the role and labor activity of the Uzbek people in the social life since ancient times, but also brings out the most beautiful customs, traditions, value and national spirit, and shows the rich spirituality and culture of our people. has been showing its originality in front of the peoples of the world.

The art of singing and its speech styles have been forming and developing over the years, showing the characteristics of various genres. In particular, the art of singing has become widely popular among the population. It is especially important that they are comprehensive in terms of genre, wide range of performance styles, and that their poetic texts mainly consist of works written in classical literature, and that they are somewhat complicated compared to European vocal art. According to musicologist S. Bekmatov, performance schools with performance styles characterized by personal and local elements have emerged. Andijan, Khorezm, Margylan, Kokan conservatory schools are among them, but the skilled performers of their time were Khamrokul Kori, Khojikhon Boltaev, Khoji Abdulaziz Abdurasulov, Mamatbuva Satorov, Jorakhan Sultanov, Mamurjon Uzokov, Fattokhan Mamadaliev , Munojot Yulchieva, Matluba Dadaboeva etc served as a solid foundation for the formation of subsequent schools of performance.[4]

Performance style and practical elements occupy a special place in the art of singing. One such element and primary process is the human voice. They have shown that the voice is considered the most important element in performance experiences. Of course, performance skills, breath, ability to control the voice, pronunciation, melody, and the balance of the creative process are also important here. It is recommended to study these features and performance skills by dividing them into the following sections. Including:

- performance skills;
- voice options and voice control;
- breath control;
- pronounce words and phrases correctly and fluently;
- the proportion of words and melody;
- rhythm issues;
- performance culture;
- stage finance;
- executive manners and ethics;
- high level of technical skill in performance;
- mental preparation in performance.[5]

It is worth mentioning modern pop singing as a new direction that was formed from the composition of Uzbek singing creativity and is widely developed today. Today, it is performed in the four main local styles that exist in Uzbek musicology as the youngest aitim genre, changing its comprehensiveness and performance style and developing. In it, mostly finger-weight poetry is chosen and sung almost without climax. Modern musical instruments are considered as the main tool in pop singing, and the fact that the rhythm given in one sheet is leading on electronic instruments can also be seen from its popularity among the population.

It is known from history that in the process of the historical formation of the peoples on earth, they embodied the most beautiful qualities of the population and carefully handed down a number of traditions and values that a person has for himself from generation to generation as a legacy. In particular, the fact that important events and events in social life, events, customs, values, customs and ceremonies related to everyday life are held as a holiday can be recognized as a proof of our above opinion. Under the influence of social, economic, political, and historical events created by people themselves, the formation and development of features related to language, spirituality, culture, and qualities, and the emergence of new trends and directions based on them in society He came to

strengthen his place and position. They were artistically decorated with customs, traditions, ceremonies, events and actions related to fulfilling certain conditions, reality, and spiritual needs in various spheres of their life. The need for them did not stop in the course of the generations following this or that event over the centuries, and on the contrary, holding and regularly continuing the rituals when the conditions required left an indelible mark on people's lives.[6]

The harmony of the voice and the instrument is very important in the performance of musical art. The process of direct speech is performed by the performer alone, in pairs, in a group or in public. Among the population, performing singers were called singers, laparchi, yallachi, termachi, bakhshi, bakhshi-oqin, dostanchi, navonoz, mughanni, singer, songwriter, teller, khalfa, poet, prose writer and khafiz. If each of the above-mentioned terms finds a full expression of the characteristics of the musical genre, "khafiz" has shown some of its aspects in connection with a number of structural features. "Khafiz" is derived from the Arabic word "khifz", which actually means "keeper", "remembering". That is probably why, in the past, the owners of professions related to performance interpretation and those who considered khifz memorization important in their actions, and embodied the aspects of interpretation, were called by this name. It should also be noted that there are Uzbek and Caucasian versions of the epics in the series "Gorogly".[7]

By the 30s of the 20th century, it was officially popular to consider the famous singers and famous singers as hafiz, performers of large-scale songs belonging to the heritage of classical music and folk songs. In 1939, the Government of the Republic of Uzbekistan established the honorary title "Khalk khafizi". Famous singers Jorakhan Sultanov, Mamurjon Uzokov and Artikkhoja Imamkhojaev were among the first to receive it. Since the first days of independence of the Republic of Uzbekistan, i.e., in 1991, this highest title given to skilled singers has been restored (after a break of almost 50 years). Ochilkhan Otakhanov, Odiljon Yusupov, Fattokhan Mamadaliev and Khasan Rajabiyar and in 1993 Mukhammadjon Karimov, Ruzmat Jumanyozov, Arifkhan Khotamov and Olmas Saidjonov, Kuvondik Iskanadarov, Eson Lutfullaev, Ismailjon and Isroiljon Vakhobov, Makhmudjon Yoldashev, Makhmudjon Tajiboev, Beknazar Do'stmurodov, Farkhod Davlatov were awarded.[8]

Performance skills with a number of internal and external features have become important in practice. Talent, knowledge, skill, perfect voice, pronunciation in singing, correct and fluent pronunciation of words, badihaguy skills, regular and continuous work on oneself, all these are the important and constant

characteristics of an artist. In the practice of singing performance, the artist, who is gaining experience in the performance, whose program includes such features, gains voice capabilities as he gets older.

Badihagoylik is a poem (music or song) created instantly without special preparation, or a musical piece that is suddenly said in connection with an event or event, or that is added to a work being performed by someone. In music, there are examples of genres such as singing, lapar, based on special art, which are characteristic of the art of big songs and bakhshis. In the performance of classical music samples, badihagoy is formed in its own way and is carried out in direct connection with the criterion of interpretation in the performance process. The performance time of the singer or musician was also realized with a creative approach to the melody or song and waiting for patterns within the requirements of the situation. In this practice, deep knowledge based on artistic and musical heritage traditions, skills in the interpretation of the practical process, and creative approach to the musical sample being performed are considered the main criteria of the singer.

The art of Uzbek national music has been developing in connection with the social life of mankind from its ancient formation to the present time. Musical samples based on different conditions were created, genre characteristics expanded on the way to its development, and created the ground for the creation of large-scale works. Creativity, which is the source of life, and the creativity contained in its system, have been illuminated to a certain extent by the masters of the past. Perfect and complex aspects of our musical heritage, rich possibilities are evidence of how important the art of music has become in human life.

Regardless of whether it is a vocal singer or a pop artist, the role and importance of musicians in its realization is considered very important. The first listener and critic of a singer is definitely a musician. The role of skilled musicians is invaluable in starting a vocal singer or pop artist on the right path. Today, Uzbek national music has a variety of musical instruments. Among them, doira, dutor, rubob, tanbur, tor, gijjak, chang, law, accordion and others should be mentioned. However, in later periods, modern electronic musical instruments also took their place and status.

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